

Calculation and Analysis of Self-Shielded Cross Sections for the High-Fidelity Neutronics Calculation of Fast Reactors

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803755

ABSTRACT

A new high-fidelity neutronics analysis tool for fast reactor calculation is built by coupling the lattice code TULIP, the SN code HYDRA and the high-fidelity neutron transport code NECP-X. TULIP is employed to generate multigroup effective cross sections for assemblies based on 0-D and 1-D cylindrical problems. HYDRA utilizes a reactor core-reflector model to perform group condensation for reflector. The cross sections are passed to NECP-X to conduct a whole-core simulation with explicit geometry description. Verification calculations were conducted based on the Superphénix 2-D and MET-1000 2-D core problems. The reference solution was obtained through continuous energy Monte Carlo calculation with NECP-MCX. Results of multigroup effective cross sections for the Superphénix problem showed good accuracy. For the fuel and reflector, the average relative difference are 0.5% and 0.8% for the 33-group structure, respectively. The maximum deviation does not exceed 4%. For eigenvalue problem, the difference of k_{eff} is -86 pcm and at most 298 pcm for Superphénix 2-D and MET-1000 2-D core problems, respectively. The root mean square error of assembly power is a maximum of 0.81%. The influence of the spectral transition effect at the core and reflector interface has been investigated. These results prove the capability of this method for yielding promising results in fast reactor calculations.

Keywords: fast reactor, multigroup cross sections, core calculation

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, fast reactor is the most promising type of reactor to solve human energy problems. Among the six next-generation reactors proposed by Generation IV International Forum, fast reactors account for three of them. However, owing to its unique neutronic characteristics, most nuclear design codes for thermal reactor are not directly applicable, which leads to the emergence of demand for fast reactor calculation tool.

In this paper, a new fast reactor neutronics calculation tool by coupling the lattice code TULIP, the SN code HYDRA [1] and the neutron transport code NECP-X [2] is presented. Compared to existing codes, the new computational method obtains cross sections for all material regions and enables high-fidelity full-core calculations based on the method of characteristics (MOC). First, the resonance calculation is performed by TULIP to generate ultrafine-group (UFG, 1968g) self-shielded cross sections. Second, based on the assembly 1-D model and core 2-D regular zone (RZ) model, UFG transport calculations are carried out by TULIP and HYDRA, respectively, to condense the cross sections into broad-group. Finally, the broad-group cross sections are passed to NECP-X to conduct a 3-D high-fidelity whole-core calculation to obtain multiplication factor and steady-state power distribution.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 briefly introduces the theory and analyses the accuracy of the multigroup cross sections. Section 3 introduces a series of problems to verify the calculation tool. Section 4 summarizes the conclusions of this paper.

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2. Methods

This method employs a 1-D cylindrical model for resonance calculation and group condensation of fuel assembly and control rod, whereas for reflector, resonance calculation is based on a homogeneous model and group condensation on a reactor core-reflector model.

2.1. Resonance calculation

The calculation procedure consists of three major parts: self-shielding for resolved resonance range by numerical integration of pointwise cross sections, self-shielding for unresolved resonance range through interpolation of the background cross section, and the calculation of scattering transfer matrix.

2.1.1. Self-shielding for resolved resonance range

In resonance calculation, the effective total, fission, and total elastic scattering cross sections in each UFG are obtained by numerical integration of pointwise cross sections using Eq. (1) in the resolved resonance range:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{x,i,g} = \frac{\int_{\Delta E_g} \sigma_{x,i}(E)\phi(E)dE}{\int_{\Delta E_g} \phi(E)dE} \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{x,i,g}$ is the effective microscopic cross section of nuclide i for reaction type x in group g . The TULIP code employs the ECCO 1968-group energy mesh [3], with each group subdivided into 200 integration points based on equal lethargy, leading to a total of approximately 400,000 hyperfine groups.

With narrow resonance approximation, the neutron spectrum of a homogeneous problem can be approximated as follows [4]:

$$\phi(E) = \frac{\Sigma_p}{E \cdot \Sigma_t(E)} \quad (2)$$

where Σ_t and Σ_p are the macroscopic total and potential cross sections, respectively. For self-shielding high-order cross sections, the l -th moment of the neutron spectrum is obtained with B_N approximation [5]:

$$\phi_l(E) = \frac{\phi(E)}{\Sigma_t(E)^l} \quad (3)$$

In the case of a heterogeneous problem, the neutron spectrum is calculated based on Wigner's rational approximation [6] by introducing escape cross section:

$$\phi_r(E) = \frac{1}{E} \frac{\Sigma_{p,r}(E) + \Sigma_{e,r}(E)}{\Sigma_{t,r}(E) + \Sigma_{e,r}(E)} \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma_{e,i,r,g} = N_{i,r} \sigma_{0,i,r,g} - \sum_{j \neq i} \Sigma_{t,j,r,g} \quad (5)$$

where $\Sigma_{e,i,r,g}$ is the macroscopic escape cross section of nuclide i for group g in region r , $\sigma_{0,i,r,g}$ is the background cross section and $N_{i,r}$ is the number density. The background cross section in Eq. (5) is determined by solving two fixed source problems based on Tone's method [7].

2.1.2. Self-shielding for unresolved resonance range

In the unresolved resonance range, the pointwise cross sections are obtained by interpolation in an additional table, given as a function of background cross section, energy and temperature. The background cross section of a homogeneous problem can be written as:

$$\sigma_{0,i,g} = \sum_{j \neq i} \frac{N_j \cdot \bar{\sigma}_{t,j,g}}{N_i} \quad (6)$$

The calculation of the effective cross section in Eq. (1) requires pointwise cross sections, which are obtained through interpolation of the background cross section in the unresolved resonance range. However, in Eq. (6), calculating the background cross section requires the effective total cross section, which makes the computation procedure an iterative process.

2.1.3. Scattering transfer matrix

The elastic scattering transfer matrix is calculated as follows [8]:

$$\sigma_s^l(g \rightarrow g') = F(l, \alpha, g \rightarrow g') \cdot \bar{\sigma}_{s,g} \quad (7)$$

$$F(l, \alpha, g \rightarrow g') = \frac{\int_{\Delta E_g} \int_{\Delta E_{g'}} \frac{P_l(\mu_s(E, E'))}{E} \sum_{n=0}^N (2n+1) a_n(E) P_n(\mu_c(E, E')) dE dE'}{\Delta E_g (1-\alpha)} \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}_{s,g}$ is the effective microscopic total elastic scattering cross section, P_l and P_n are the l -th and n -th order Legendre polynomials, respectively, a_n is the n -th order Legendre polynomial coefficient in the ENDF library, μ_s and μ_c are the cosines of the scattering angle in the laboratory system and center-of-mass system, respectively, $\alpha = (A-1)^2 / (A+1)^2$ and A is the atomic mass.

It can be observed that the scattering transfer function $F(l, \alpha, g \rightarrow g')$ is only related to nuclide and energy group structure. Therefore, once the $\bar{\sigma}_{s,g}$ is determined, the scattering transfer matrix can be directly obtained by Eq. (7) with a pre-calculated table of scattering transfer functions.

2.2. Group condensation

Considering the computational resource requirements, it would be impractical to perform a whole-core simulation based on the 1968-group cross sections, and group condensation is required to accelerate the calculation. For fuel assembly and control rod, the weighting spectrum is obtained by solving a UFG 1-D problem, which is exactly the same as that employed in the resonance calculation. For reflector, however, there is no fissile material and the neutron spectrum is largely determined by the leaking-in neutron source from the neighboring assemblies; therefore, a UFG 2-D transport calculation based on the reactor core RZ model is solved with the SN method. The super homogenization method [9] was employed to ensure reaction rate preservation before and after condensation. Table I shows the 33-group structure. For the 195-group structure, approximately every 10 groups of the 1968-group structure are condensed into one group. Figure 1 shows the group condensation models.

Table I. 33-group structure.

Group index	Upper boundary (UB)/MeV	Group index	UB/MeV	Group index	UB/MeV	Group index	UB/MeV
1	19.6403E+01	10	1.8316E-01	19	2.0347E-03	28	2.2603E-05
2	10.0000E+01	11	1.1109E-01	20	1.2341E-03	29	1.3710E-05
3	6.0653E+00	12	6.7380E-02	21	7.4852E-04	30	8.3153E-06
4	3.6788E+00	13	4.0868E-02	22	4.5400E-04	31	4.0000E-06
5	2.2313E+00	14	2.4788E-02	23	3.0432E-04	32	5.4000E-07
6	1.3534E+00	15	1.5034E-02	24	1.4862E-04	33	1.0000E-07
7	8.2085E-01	16	9.1188E-03	25	9.1661E-05		
8	4.9787E-01	17	5.5308E-03	26	6.7904E-05		
9	3.0197E-01	18	3.3546E-03	27	4.0169E-05		

Figure 1. Group condensation models for fuel assembly and reflector.

2.3. Cross-section verification

The validity of the generated cross sections was verified with the Superphénix 2-D core benchmark problem [10], as shown in Figure 2. Results of region-wise broad-group macroscopic total cross sections were compared with Monte Carlo solutions obtained from NECP-MCX [11]. The Monte Carlo calculations presented in this section and all following core simulations were performed under the same computational parameters: 200 inactive cycles, 400 active cycles, and 3,000,000 particles per cycle.

Figure 2. Superphénix 2-D core problem.

Figure 3 shows the 33-group and 195-group macroscopic total cross sections of the center fuel pellet of assemblies ① and ②, respectively. To mitigate statistical fluctuations of Monte Carlo solutions at extreme energy ranges, the comparative cross sections is confined to the range from 148.6 eV (23rd group) to 19.6 MeV (1st group) for 33-group structure and 190.8 eV (139th group) to 15.2 MeV (4th group) for 195-group structure.

Figure 3. Macroscopic total cross sections of the center fuel pellet of assemblies ① and ②.

Due to the long mean free path of neutrons in fast reactor, cross sections of fuel assemblies exhibit no significant variation with positional changes. Furthermore, cross sections derived from the 1-D model

demonstrate great agreement with those obtained via 2-D core Monte Carlo calculation, with an average difference of only 0.3% for 33-group structure and 0.5% for 195-group structure. Although 33-group shows better result, it is believed that the error cancellation occurred in the low energy range.

Figure 4 shows the 33-group and 195-group macroscopic total cross sections of the reflector assembly ③. TULIP-A is the TULIP result obtained in the homogeneous reflector model using the fission spectrum of U-238 as the fission source. TULIP-B is the HYDRA result obtained by condensing the UFG cross sections from TULIP based on the core RZ model. It is observed that the TULIP-B result outperforms TULIP-A. The maximum difference is greatly reduced after considering the spectral transition effect.

Figure 4. Macroscopic total cross sections of the assembly ③.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, verifications were conducted on two 2-D core problems. The reference solution was obtained through continuous energy Monte Carlo calculation with NECP-MCX. The 33-group structure was selected to save the computation time and outflow correction and P1 approximation were tested. The transport calculation was performed by NECP-X with the method of characteristics. The calculation conditions are shown in Table II.

Table II. Transport calculation conditions.

Parameter	Value
Azimuthal angle	32
Polar angle	6
Ray spacing	0.03 cm
k_{eff} criteria	1.0e-6
Fission rate criteria	1.0e-4

3.1. Superphénix 2-D core problem

The region-wise macroscopic cross sections analyzed in section 2.3 were subsequently used in transport calculation to obtain multiplication factor and steady-state power distribution of the Superphénix 2-D core. Table III summarizes the k_{eff} value compared to the reference. Figure 5 shows the relative difference in assembly-wise radial power distribution. (T, N) stands for TULIP and NECP-X. (T, H, N) stands for TULIP, HYDRA and NECP-X. The distinction between (T, N) and (T, H, N) lies in the fact that the latter employs HYDRA to determine the broad-group cross sections of the reflector, considering the spectral transition effect at the core and reflector interface. However, the impact of this effect is not observed in this problem. Two cases yielded almost identical results, with a difference of 68 pcm for multiplication factor and a root-mean-square (RMS) error of 0.39% for power distribution. Besides, under P1 approximation, the power of peripheral assemblies increased while that of inner assemblies decreased, resulting in a reduced power gradient across the reactor core.

Table III. Comparison of k_{eff} value for Superphénix 2-D core problem.

Code	k_{eff}	Difference (pcm)
NECP-MCX	1.06607 ± 0.00002	
(T, N), outflow	1.06675	68
(T, H, N), outflow	1.06675	68
(T, H, N), P1	1.06521	-86

Figure 5. Relative difference in assembly-wise radial power distribution of Superphénix 2-D core problem.

3.2. MET-1000 2-D core problem

The results of the Superphénix problem suggest that the spectral transition effect is ignorable, which is beyond our expectation. For further verification, additional calculations were conducted on two MET-1000 2-D core problems [12] to analyze the impact of neutron absorbers, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. MET-1000 2-D core problems.

Table IV summarizes the k_{eff} value compared to the reference. Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the relative difference in assembly-wise radial power distribution of Case A and Case B, respectively. It can be seen that, different from the Superphénix 2-D core, the spectral transition effect could induce deviation up to hundreds of pcm in these problems. The power distribution obtained under (T, H, N) also demonstrated significant refinement.

The reactivity difference between “(T, N), outflow” and “(T, H, N), outflow” is 785 pcm for Case B, which exceeds twice that of Case A (349 pcm). Figure 9 (a) shows the total fluxes of assemblies ① ~ ④ of Figure 6. The results show that, for Case B, the total flux of the fuel assembly is lower while that of the reflector is higher, which means the reflector takes a more important role in Case B compared to Case A. Figure 9 (b) shows the total fluxes of assemblies ① and ③ of Figure 2. It can be observed that, due to the thick breeder blanket, the neutron flux decreased to almost zero in the reflector, which explains why modifying the cross sections of the reflector had almost no impact on the results of the Superphénix 2-D core problem.

From these results, it is concluded that neutron absorbers like control rod and breeder blanket can reduce neutron flux in the reflector, thereby diminishing the influence of the spectral transition effect at the core and reflector interface.

Table IV. Comparison of k_{eff} value for MET-1000 2-D core problems.

Code	k_{eff}		Difference (pcm)	
	Case A	Case B	Case A	Case B
NECP-MCX	1.06540 ± 0.00002	1.24371 ± 0.00002		
(T, N), outflow	1.06470	1.23967	-70	-404
(T, H, N), outflow	1.06819	1.24752	279	381
(T, H, N), P1	1.06590	1.24669	50	298

Figure 7. Relative difference in assembly-wise radial power distribution of Case A.

Figure 8. Relative difference in assembly-wise radial power distribution of Case B.

Figure 9. Total fluxes of fuel and reflector assemblies in the MET-1000 and Superphénix 2-D core problems.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A new high-fidelity fast reactor calculation tool by coupling TULIP, HYDRA and NECP-X has been presented. In the coupled system, the resonance calculation is conducted by TULIP to obtain UFG self-shielded cross sections. Following that, UFG transport calculation is carried out based on 1-D cylindrical problem to condense the 1968-group cross sections into broad-group. For the reflector, the HYDRA code is employed to perform a UFG 2-D transport calculation based on a core RZ model to condense

the cross sections into broad-group. Finally, the whole-core calculation is carried out by NECP-X with the MOC solver to obtain multiplication factor and steady-state power distribution.

Numerical results for 2-D core problems showed that the coupled code system has successfully managed to conduct fast reactor calculation and provides results with sufficient accuracy. The difference of k_{eff} was -86 pcm and at most 298 pcm for Superphénix 2-D and MET-1000 2-D core problems, respectively. The root mean square error of assembly power was a maximum of only 0.81%.

Currently, verification is limited to 2-D problems. And as such, the 2-D SN calculation in HYDRA is effectively 1-D in nature. Future work will involve validation of the method for 3-D core problems, and we will focus on addressing the convergence issue in higher-order transport calculations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 12375174, No. U24B2010) and Innovative Scientific Program of China National Nuclear Corporation.

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